

**A Robust Coordinated Expansion
Planning Model for Wind Farm-
Integrated Power Systems with Flexibility
Sources Using Affine Policies**

Extended Formulation

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1. Deterministic Coordinated Expansion Planning Model:

$$\begin{aligned} \min & \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} ic_l \cdot z_l + \sum_{r \in \Omega^R} ic_r \cdot z_r + \sum_{s \in \Omega^S} ic_s \cdot z_s + \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} ic_u \cdot z_u + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} ic_w \cdot z_w \\ & + \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{uto} + \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{wto} + \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{b \in \Omega^B} \rho_o \cdot vol_b \cdot p_{bto} \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & p_{bto} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^c + \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^d - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | s(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | r(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{u \in \Omega^{U^b}} p_{uto} + \sum_{w \in \Omega^{W^b}} p_{wto} \\ & = \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} \bar{p}_{dto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq p_{uto} \leq p_u^{\max} \cdot z_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1c)$$

$$-rd_u \leq p_{uto} - p_{u(t-1)o} \leq ru_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1d)$$

$$0 \leq p_{wto} \leq \bar{p}_{wto} \cdot z_u \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{bto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1f)$$

$$e_s^{\min} \cdot z_s \leq e_s^0 \cdot z_s + \sum_{t=1}^t \left(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^c - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^d \right) \leq e_s^{\max} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T | t < 24, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1g)$$

$$\sum_{t=1}^{24} \left(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^c - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^d \right) = 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1h)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^c \leq p_s^{c_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^c \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1i)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^d \leq p_s^{d_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^d \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1j)$$

$$x_{sto}^c + x_{sto}^d \leq z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1k)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \leq m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1l)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \geq -m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1m)$$

$$-p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} - \Delta p_{lto} \leq p_{lto} \leq p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} + \Delta p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1n)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto} \leq \Delta \bar{p}_{lto} \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1o)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto} \leq \Delta \bar{p}_{lto} \cdot x_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1p)$$

$$x_{lto} \leq z_l \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1q)$$

$$-\theta^{\max} \leq \theta_{bto} \leq \theta^{\max} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1r)$$

$$\theta_{to}^{ref} = 0 \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (1s)$$

2. Robust Coordinated Expansion Planning Model:

$$\min \sigma \quad (2a)$$

First-Stage Constraints:

$$x_{lto} \leq z_l \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2b)$$

$$x_{sto}^c + x_{sto}^d \leq z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2c)$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Independent Variables:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} ic_l \cdot z_l - \sum_{r \in \Omega^R} ic_r \cdot z_r - \sum_{s \in \Omega^S} ic_s \cdot z_s - \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} ic_u \cdot z_u - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} ic_w \cdot z_w - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{uto} \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{wto} - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{b \in \Omega^B} \rho_o \cdot vol_b \cdot p_{bto} \geq 0 \quad : \quad \gamma^{OBJ} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & p_{bto} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^c + \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^d - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | s(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | r(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{uto} + \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{wto} \\ & \geq \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} \tilde{p}_{dto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma^{PBC} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2e)$$

$$0 \leq p_{uto} \leq p_u^{\max} \cdot z_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma^{TGL} \geq 0 \quad (2f)$$

$$-rd_u \leq p_{uto} - p_{u(t-1)o} \leq ru_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{uto}^{LRT} \geq 0, \gamma_{uto}^{URT} \geq 0 \quad (2g)$$

$$0 \leq p_{wto} \leq \tilde{p}_{wto} \cdot z_w \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{wto}^{WGL} \geq 0 \quad (2h)$$

$$e_s^{\min} \cdot z_s \leq e_s^0 \cdot z_s + \sum_{t'=1}^t \left(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^c - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^d \right) \leq e_s^{\max} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T | t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : \gamma_{sto}^{LCD} \geq 0, \gamma_{sto}^{UCD} \geq 0 \quad (2i)$$

$$\sum_{t'=1}^{24} \left(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^c - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^d \right) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{so}^{CDE+} \geq 0 \quad (2j)$$

$$-\sum_{t'=1}^{24} \left(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^c - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^d \right) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{so}^{CDE-} \geq 0 \quad (2k)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^c \leq p_s^{c_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^c \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{sto}^{SCL} \geq 0 \quad (2l)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^d \leq p_s^{d_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^d \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{sto}^{SDL} \geq 0 \quad (2m)$$

$$-p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} - \Delta p_{lto} \leq p_{lto} \leq p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} + \Delta p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{lto}^{DTRL} \geq 0, \gamma_{lto}^{DTRU} \geq 0 \quad (2n)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto} \leq \Delta \tilde{p}_{lto} \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{lto}^{DTRZ} \geq 0 \quad (2o)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto} \leq \Delta \tilde{p}_{lto} \cdot x_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \gamma_{lto}^{DTRX} \geq 0 \quad (2p)$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Dependent Variables:

$$0 \leq p_{bto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2q)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \leq m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2r)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \geq -m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2s)$$

$$-\theta^{\max} \leq \theta_{bto} \leq \theta^{\max} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2t)$$

$$\theta_{to}^{ref} = 0 \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (2u)$$

where, the uncertainty set pertaining to the primal formulation can be represented as follows:

$$\Omega^\Gamma = \{ \Omega^{\Gamma_D}, \Omega^{\Gamma_W}, \Omega^{\Gamma_R} \} \quad (3a)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma_D} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{p}_{dto} = \bar{p}_{dto} + p_{dto}^+ - p_{dto}^- \\ 0 \leq p_{dto}^+ \leq \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \\ 0 \leq p_{dto}^- \leq \hat{p}_{dto}^- \end{array} \right\} \quad d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (3b)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma_W} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{p}_{wto} = \bar{p}_{wto} + p_{wto}^+ - p_{wto}^- \\ 0 \leq p_{wto}^+ \leq \hat{p}_{wto}^+ \\ 0 \leq p_{wto}^- \leq \hat{p}_{wto}^- \end{array} \right\} \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (3c)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma_R} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \tilde{p}_{lto} = \Delta \bar{p}_{lto} + \Delta p_{lto}^+ - \Delta p_{lto}^- \\ 0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^+ \leq \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^+ \\ 0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^- \leq \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \end{array} \right\} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (3d)$$

Also, the conservatism of the optimal solution can be controlled as follows:

$$\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \left(\frac{p_{dto}^+}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} + \frac{p_{dto}^-}{\hat{p}_{dto}^-} \right) + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \left(\frac{p_{wto}^+}{\hat{p}_{wto}^+} + \frac{p_{wto}^-}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \right) + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \left(\frac{\Delta p_{lto}^+}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^+} + \frac{\Delta p_{lto}^-}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \right) \leq \Upsilon_{to} \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (3e)$$

To obtain a more tractable formulation, the polyhedral uncertainty set can be recast as given below:

$$\Omega^\Gamma = \{ \Omega^{\Gamma^D}, \Omega^{\Gamma^W}, \Omega^{\Gamma^R} \} \quad (4a)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma^D} = \{ \tilde{p}_{dto} = \bar{p}_{dto} + p_{dto}^+ \quad ; \quad 0 \leq p_{dto}^+ \leq \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \quad d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \lambda_{dto}^D \geq 0 \} \quad (4b)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma^W} = \{ \tilde{p}_{wto} = \bar{p}_{wto} - p_{wto}^- \quad ; \quad 0 \leq p_{wto}^- \leq \hat{p}_{wto}^- \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \lambda_{wto}^W \geq 0 \} \quad (4c)$$

$$\Omega^{\Gamma^R} = \{ \Delta \tilde{p}_{lto} = \Delta \bar{p}_{lto} - \Delta p_{lto}^- \quad ; \quad 0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^- \leq \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \lambda_{lto}^R \geq 0 \} \quad (4d)$$

and

$$\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \left(\frac{p_{dto}^+}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \right) + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \left(\frac{p_{wto}^-}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \right) + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \left(\frac{\Delta p_{lto}^-}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \right) \leq \Upsilon_{to} \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad : \quad \lambda_{to}^Y \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4e)$$

3. Reformulating Robust Coordinated Expansion Planning Model Using Affine Policies:

Affine policies:

$$p_{uto} = p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (8a)$$

$$p_{wto} = p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (8b)$$

$$p_{sto}^c = p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (8c)$$

$$p_{sto}^d = p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (8d)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto} = \Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (8e)$$

a. Using LDRs in the Formulation

$$\min \sigma \quad (9a)$$

s.t.

First-Stage Constraints:

$$x_{lto} \leq z_l \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9b)$$

$$x_{sto}^c + x_{sto}^d \leq z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9c)$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Independent Variables:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} ic_l \cdot z_l - \sum_{r \in \Omega^R} ic_r \cdot z_r - \sum_{s \in \Omega^S} ic_s \cdot z_s - \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} ic_u \cdot z_u - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} ic_w \cdot z_w - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{b \in \Omega^B} \rho_o \cdot vol_b \cdot p_{bto} \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot (p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot (p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} (p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \\ & + \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} (p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \\ & + \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} (p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \end{aligned} \quad (9e)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & + \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} (p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \\ & + p_{bto} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | s(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | r(l)=b} p_{lto} \geq \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} (\bar{p}_{dto} + p_{dto}^+) \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned}$$

$$0 \leq (p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \leq p_u^{\max} \cdot z_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9f)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -rd_u & \leq (p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) - (p_{u(t-1)o}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{du(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{d(t-1)o}^+) \\ & + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wu(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{w(t-1)o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lu(t-1)o}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l(t-1)o}^-) \leq ru_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (9g)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 & \leq (p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \\ & \leq (\bar{p}_{wto} - p_{wto}^-) \cdot z_w \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (9h)$$

$$\begin{aligned} e_s^{\min} \cdot z_s & \leq e_s^0 + \sum_{t'=1}^t (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) \\ & - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \leq e_s^{\max} \cdot z_s \end{aligned} \quad (9i)$$

$$s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9j)$$

$$-\sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9k)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \leq p_{sto}^{c_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^c \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9l)$$

$$0 \leq p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \leq p_{sto}^{d_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^d \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9m)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{ltb} - (\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^-) \leq p_{lto} \\ & \leq p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} + (\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^-) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (9n)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \leq \quad (9o)$$

$$(\Delta \bar{p}_{lto} - \Delta p_{lto}^-) \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \leq \quad (9p)$$

$$(\Delta \bar{p}_{lto} - \Delta p_{lto}^-) \cdot x_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Dependent Variables:

$$0 \leq p_{bto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9q)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \leq m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9r)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \geq -m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9s)$$

$$-\theta^{\max} \leq \theta_{bto} \leq \theta^{\max} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9t)$$

$$\theta_{to}^{ref} = 0 \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (9u)$$

where,

$$0 \leq p_{dto}^+ \leq \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \quad d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (10a)$$

$$0 \leq p_{wto}^- \leq \hat{p}_{wto}^- \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (10b)$$

$$0 \leq \Delta p_{lto}^- \leq \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (10c)$$

$$\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \left(\frac{p_{dto}^+}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \right) + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \left(\frac{p_{wto}^-}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \right) + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \left(\frac{\Delta p_{lto}^-}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \right) \leq \Upsilon_{to} \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (10d)$$

b. Rearranging LDRs in the Formulation

$$\min \sigma \quad (11a)$$

s.t.

First-Stage Constraints:

$$x_{lto} \leq z_l \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11b)$$

$$x_{sto}^c + x_{sto}^d \leq z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11c)$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Independent Variables:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} ic_l \cdot z_l - \sum_{r \in \Omega^R} ic_r \cdot z_r - \sum_{s \in \Omega^S} ic_s \cdot z_s - \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} ic_u \cdot z_u - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} ic_w \cdot z_w - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{b \in \Omega^B} \rho_o \cdot vol_b \cdot p_{bto} \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{uto}^n - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{wto}^n \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \left(\left(\sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{duto}^a \right) + \left(\sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{dwto}^a \right) \right) \cdot p_{dto}^+ \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} \left(\left(\sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{w'uto}^a \right) + \left(\sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{w'wto}^a \right) \right) \cdot p_{w'to}^- \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \left(\left(\sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{luto}^a \right) + \left(\sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{lwto}^a \right) \right) \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{uto}^n + \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{wto}^n + p_{bto} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | s(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | r(l)=b} p_{lto} \\ & - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \left(\sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{dsto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{dsto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{duto}^a - \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{dwto}^a \right) \cdot p_{dto}^+ \\ & - \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} \left(\sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{w'sto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{w'sto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{w'luto}^a - \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{w'wto}^a \right) \cdot p_{w'to}^- \\ & - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \left(\sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{lsto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{lsto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{luto}^a - \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{lwto}^a \right) \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \\ & - \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} p_{dto}^+ \geq \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} \bar{p}_{dto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (11e)$$

$$p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11f)$$

$$p_u^{\max} \cdot z_u - (p_{uto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \geq 0 \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11g)$$

$$p_{uto}^n - p_{u(t-1)o}^n + (\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) - (\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{du(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{d(t-1)o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wu(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{w(t-1)o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lu(t-1)o}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l(t-1)o}^-) \geq -rd_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11h)$$

$$-p_{uto}^n + p_{u(t-1)o}^n - (\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{duto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wuto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{luto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) + (\sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{du(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{d(t-1)o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wu(t-1)o}^a \cdot p_{w(t-1)o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lu(t-1)o}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l(t-1)o}^-) \geq -ru_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11i)$$

$$p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11j)$$

$$p_{wto}^- \cdot z_w - (p_{wto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dwto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} p_{w'wto}^a \cdot p_{w'to}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lwto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \geq -\bar{p}_{wto}^- \cdot z_w \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11k)$$

$$e_s^0 + \sum_{t'=1}^t (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \geq e_s^{\min} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11l)$$

$$-e_s^0 - \sum_{t'=1}^t (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \geq -e_s^{\max} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11m)$$

$$\sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dt'o}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wt'o}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lt'o}^-)) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11n)$$

$$-\sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot (p_{st'o}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot (p_{st'o}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wst'o}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lst'o}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-)) \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11o)$$

$$p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11p)$$

$$-(p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{ca} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{ca} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \geq -p_{sto}^{c_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^c \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11q)$$

$$p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11r)$$

$$-(p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} p_{dsto}^{da} \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} p_{wsto}^{da} \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} p_{lsto}^{da} \cdot \Delta p_{lto}^-) \geq -p_{sto}^{d_{\max}} \cdot x_{sto}^d \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11s)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq -p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} - p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11t)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq -p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{lto} + p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11u)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11v)$$

$$-(\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^-) \quad (11w)$$

$$-\Delta p_{lto}^- \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \geq -\Delta \bar{p}_{lto}^- \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11x)$$

$$-(\Delta p_{lto}^n + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \Delta p_{dlto}^a \cdot p_{dto}^+ + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \Delta p_{wlto}^a \cdot p_{wto}^- + \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta p_{l'lto}^a \cdot \Delta p_{l'to}^-) \quad (11y)$$

$$-\Delta p_{lto}^- \cdot x_{lto} \geq -\Delta \bar{p}_{lto}^- \cdot x_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Dependent Variables:

$$0 \leq p_{bto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11z)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \leq m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11za)$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \geq -m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11zb)$$

$$-\theta^{\max} \leq \theta_{bto} \leq \theta^{\max} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11zc)$$

$$\theta_{to}^{ref} = 0 \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (11zd)$$

c. Using Duality Theory

$$\min \sigma \quad (12)$$

s.t.

First-Stage Constraints:

$$x_{lto} \leq z_l \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (13)$$

$$x_{sto}^c + x_{sto}^d \leq z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (14)$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Independent Variables:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sigma - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} ic_l \cdot z_l - \sum_{r \in \Omega^R} ic_r \cdot z_r - \sum_{s \in \Omega^S} ic_s \cdot z_s - \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} ic_u \cdot z_u - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} ic_w \cdot z_w - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{b \in \Omega^B} \rho_o \cdot vol_b \cdot p_{bto} \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{uto}^n - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{u \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{wto}^n - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,OBJ} \\ & - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,OBJ} - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{R,OBJ} - \sum_{o \in \Omega^O} \sum_{t \in \Omega^T} \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{to}^{Y,OBJ} \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15a)$$

$$\lambda_{dto}^{D,OBJ} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{to}^{Y,OBJ} \geq \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{duto}^a + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{dwto}^a \quad d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (15b)$$

$$\lambda_{wto}^{W,OBJ} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{to}^{Y,OBJ} \geq \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{wuto}^a + \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_{w'} \cdot p_{w'wto}^a \quad w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (15c)$$

$$\lambda_{lto}^{R,OBJ} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{to}^{Y,OBJ} \geq \sum_{u \in \Omega^U} \rho_o \cdot oc_u \cdot p_{luto}^a + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \rho_o \cdot oc_w \cdot p_{lwto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (15c)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^{cn} + \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{sto}^{dn} + \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{uto}^n + \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{wto}^n + p_{bto} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | s(l)=b} p_{lto} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L | r(l)=b} p_{lto} \\
& - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{bdto}^{D,PBC} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{bwto}^{W,PBC} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{blto}^{R,PBC} \\
& - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{bto}^{Y,PBC} \geq \sum_{d \in \Omega^{Db}} \bar{p}_{dto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O
\end{aligned} \tag{16a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lambda_{bdto}^{D,PBC} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{bto}^{Y,PBC} \geq \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{dsto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{dsto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{duto}^a \\
& - \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{dwto}^a + \left| \Omega^{Db} \right| \quad b \in \Omega^B, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{16b}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lambda_{bwto}^{W,PBC} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{bto}^{Y,PBC} \geq \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{wsto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{wsto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{wuto}^a \\
& - \sum_{w' \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{w'wto}^a \quad b \in \Omega^B, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{16c}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lambda_{blto}^{R,PBC} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{bto}^{Y,PBC} \geq \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{lsto}^{ca} - \sum_{s \in \Omega^{Sb}} p_{lsto}^{da} - \sum_{u \in \Omega^{Ub}} p_{luto}^a \\
& - \sum_{w \in \Omega^{Wb}} p_{lwto}^a \quad b \in \Omega^B, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{16d}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& p_{uto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{udto}^{D,LTGL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{uwto}^{W,LTGL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ulto}^{R,LTGL} \\
& - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LTGL} \geq 0 \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O
\end{aligned} \tag{17a}$$

$$\lambda_{udto}^{D,LTGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LTGL} \geq -p_{duto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \tag{17b}$$

$$\lambda_{uwto}^{W,LTGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LTGL} \geq -p_{wuto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \tag{17c}$$

$$\lambda_{ulto}^{R,LTGL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LTGL} \geq -p_{luto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \tag{17d}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& p_u^{\max} \cdot z_u - p_{uto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{udto}^{D,UTGL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{uwto}^{W,UTGL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ulto}^{R,UTGL} \\
& - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,UTGL} \geq 0 \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O
\end{aligned} \tag{18a}$$

$$\lambda_{uto}^{D,UTGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,UTGL} \geq p_{duto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (18b)$$

$$\lambda_{uw'to}^{W,UTGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,UTGL} \geq p_{w'uto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (18c)$$

$$\lambda_{ulto}^{R,UTGL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{ulto}^{Y,UTGL} \geq p_{luto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (18d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & p_{uto}^n - p_{u(t-1)o}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{udto}^{D,LRT} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{uw'to}^{W,LRT} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ulto}^{R,LRT} - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LRT} \\ & - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{d(t-1)o}^+ \cdot \lambda_{ud(t-1)o}^{D,LRT} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{w(t-1)o}^- \cdot \lambda_{uw'(t-1)o}^{W,LRT} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{l(t-1)o}^- \cdot \lambda_{ul(t-1)o}^{R,LRT} - \Upsilon_{(t-1)o} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,LRT} \\ & \geq -rd_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (19a)$$

$$\lambda_{udto}^{D,LRT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LRT} \geq -p_{duto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (19b)$$

$$\lambda_{ud(t-1)o}^{D,LRT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{d(t-1)o}^+} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,LRT} \geq p_{du(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (19c)$$

$$\lambda_{uw'to}^{W,LRT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LRT} \geq -p_{w'uto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (19d)$$

$$\lambda_{uw'(t-1)o}^{W,LRT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,LRT} \geq p_{w'u(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (19e)$$

$$\lambda_{ulto}^{R,LRT} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,LRT} \geq -p_{luto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (19f)$$

$$\lambda_{ul(t-1)o}^{R,LRT} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l(t-1)o}^-} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,LRT} \geq p_{lu(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (19g)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -p_{uto}^n + p_{u(t-1)o}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{udto}^{D,URT} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{uw'to}^{W,URT} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ulto}^{R,URT} - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,URT} \\ & + \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{d(t-1)o}^+ \cdot \lambda_{ud(t-1)o}^{D,URT} + \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{w(t-1)o}^- \cdot \lambda_{uw'(t-1)o}^{W,URT} + \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{l(t-1)o}^- \cdot \lambda_{ul(t-1)o}^{R,URT} + \Upsilon_{(t-1)o} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,URT} \\ & \geq -ru_u \quad u \in \Omega^U, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (20a)$$

$$\lambda_{udto}^{D,URT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,URT} \geq p_{duto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (20b)$$

$$\lambda_{ud(t-1)o}^{D,URT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{d(t-1)o}^+} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,URT} \geq -p_{du(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (20c)$$

$$\lambda_{uw'to}^{W,URT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,URT} \geq p_{w'uto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (20d)$$

$$\lambda_{uw'(t-1)o}^{W,URT} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'(t-1)o}^-} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,URT} \geq -p_{w'u(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (20e)$$

$$\lambda_{ulto}^{R,URT} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{uto}^{Y,URT} \geq p_{luto}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (20f)$$

$$\lambda_{ul(t-1)o}^{R,URT} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l(t-1)o}^-} \cdot \lambda_{u(t-1)o}^{Y,URT} \geq -p_{lu(t-1)o}^a \quad u \in \Omega^U, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (20g)$$

$$p_{wto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{wdto}^{D,LWGL} - \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{w'to}^- \cdot \lambda_{ww'to}^{W,LWGL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wlto}^{R,LWGL} - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,LWGL} \geq 0 \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (21a)$$

$$\lambda_{wdto}^{D,LWGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,LWGL} \geq -p_{dwto}^a \quad w \in \Omega^W, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (21b)$$

$$\lambda_{ww'to}^{W,LWGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,LWGL} \geq -p_{w'wto}^a \quad w, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (21c)$$

$$\lambda_{wlto}^{R,LWGL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,LWGL} \geq -p_{lwto}^a \quad w \in \Omega^W, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (21d)$$

$$-p_{wto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{wdto}^{D,UWGL} - \sum_{w' \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{w'to}^- \cdot \lambda_{ww'to}^{W,UWGL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wlto}^{R,UWGL} - \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,UWGL} \geq -\bar{p}_{wto} \cdot z_w \quad w \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \quad (22a)$$

$$\lambda_{wdto}^{D,UWGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,UWGL} \geq p_{dwto}^a \quad w \in \Omega^W, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (22b)$$

$$\lambda_{ww'to}^{W,UWGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,UWGL} \geq p_{w'wto}^a + z_w \quad w, w' \in \Omega^W \mid w = w', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (22c)$$

$$\lambda_{ww'to}^{W,UWGL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,UWGL} \geq p_{w'to}^a \quad w, w' \in \Omega^W \mid w \neq w', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (22c)$$

$$\lambda_{wlt o}^{R,UWGL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{Y,UWGL} \geq p_{lwt o}^a \quad w \in \Omega^W, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (22d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} e_s^0 + \sum_{t'=1}^t (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^{cn} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^{dn}) - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dt'o}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdt'o}^{D,LCD} - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wt'o}^- \cdot \lambda_{swt'o}^{W,LCD} - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lt'o}^- \cdot \lambda_{slt'o}^{R,LCD} \\ - \sum_{t'=1}^t \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCD} \geq e_s^{\min} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (23a)$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,LCD} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCD} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{dsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{dsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (23b)$$

$$\lambda_{sw'to}^{W,LCD} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCD} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{w'st'o}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{w'st'o}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (23c)$$

$$\lambda_{slt o}^{R,LCD} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCD} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{lst o}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{lst o}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (23d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -e_s^0 - \sum_{t'=1}^t (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'o}^{cn} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'o}^{dn}) - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dt'o}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdt'o}^{D,UCD} - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wt'o}^- \cdot \lambda_{swt'o}^{W,UCD} - \sum_{t'=1}^t \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lt'o}^- \cdot \lambda_{slt'o}^{R,UCD} \\ - \sum_{t'=1}^t \Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,UCD} \geq -e_s^{\max} \cdot z_s \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (24a)$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,UCD} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,UCD} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{dsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{dsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (24b)$$

$$\lambda_{sw'to}^{W,UCD} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,UCD} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{w'st o}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{w'st o}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (24c)$$

$$\lambda_{s'to}^{R,UCD} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,UCD} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{lsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{lsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T \mid t < 24, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (24d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'b}^{cn} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'b}^{dn}) - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dt'b}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdt'b}^{D,CDE+} - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wt'b}^- \cdot \lambda_{swt'b}^{W,CDE+} - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{l't'b}^- \cdot \lambda_{slt'b}^{R,CDE+} \\ & - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE+} \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (25a)$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,CDE+} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE+} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{dsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{dsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (25b)$$

$$\lambda_{sw'to}^{W,LCE+} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCE+} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{w'sto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{w'sto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (25c)$$

$$\lambda_{s'to}^{R,CDE+} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE+} \geq -(\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{lsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{lsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (25d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{st'b}^{cn} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{st'b}^{dn}) - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dt'b}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdt'b}^{D,CDE-} - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wt'b}^- \cdot \lambda_{swt'b}^{W,CDE-} - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{l't'b}^- \cdot \lambda_{slt'b}^{R,CDE-} \\ & - \sum_{t'=1}^{24} Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE-} \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (26a)$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,CDE-} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE-} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{dsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{dsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (26b)$$

$$\lambda_{sw'to}^{W,LCE-} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LCE-} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{w'sto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{w'sto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (26c)$$

$$\lambda_{s'to}^{R,CDE-} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,CDE-} \geq (\zeta_s^c \cdot p_{lsto}^{ca} - \frac{1}{\zeta_s^d} \cdot p_{lsto}^{da}) \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (26d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & p_{sto}^{cn} - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdto}^{D,LSCL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{swto}^{W,LSCL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^- \cdot \lambda_{slt'o}^{R,LSCL} \\ & - Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSCL} \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \end{aligned} \quad (27a)$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,LSCL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSCL} \geq -p_{dsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (27b)$$

$$\lambda_{swto}^{W,LSCL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSCL} \geq -p_{wsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (27c)$$

$$\lambda_{ssto}^{R,LSCL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSCL} \geq -p_{lsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (27d)$$

$$-p_{sto}^{cn} - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdto}^{D,USCL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{swto}^{W,USCL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ssto}^{R,USCL} \quad (28a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USCL} \geq -p_{sto}^{cmax} \cdot x_{sto}^c \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,USCL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USCL} \geq p_{dsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (28b)$$

$$\lambda_{swto}^{W,USCL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USCL} \geq p_{wsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (28c)$$

$$\lambda_{ssto}^{R,USCL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USCL} \geq p_{lsto}^{ca} \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (28d)$$

$$p_{sto}^{dn} - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdto}^{D,LSDL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{swto}^{W,LSDL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ssto}^{R,LSDL} \quad (29a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSDL} \geq 0 \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,LSDL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSDL} \geq -p_{dsto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (29b)$$

$$\lambda_{swto}^{W,LSDL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSDL} \geq -p_{wsto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (29c)$$

$$\lambda_{ssto}^{R,LSDL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,LSDL} \geq -p_{lsto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (29d)$$

$$-p_{sto}^{dn} - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{sdto}^{D,USDL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{swto}^{W,USDL} - \sum_{l \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{ssto}^{R,USDL} \quad (30a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USDL} \geq -p_{sto}^{dmax} \cdot x_{sto}^d \quad s \in \Omega^S, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{sdto}^{D,USDL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USDL} \geq p_{dsto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (30b)$$

$$\lambda_{swto}^{W,USDL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USDL} \geq p_{wsto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (30c)$$

$$\lambda_{slto}^{R,USDL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{sto}^{Y,USDL} \geq p_{slto}^{da} \quad s \in \Omega^S, l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (30d)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,DTRL} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'to}^{R,DTRL} \quad (31a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRL} \geq -p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{ltb} - p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{ldto}^{D,DTRL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRL} \geq -\Delta p_{dltto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (31b)$$

$$\lambda_{lwto}^{W,DTRL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRL} \geq -\Delta p_{w'lto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (31c)$$

$$\lambda_{ll'to}^{R,DTRL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRL} \geq -\Delta p_{l'lto}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (31d)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRU} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,DTRU} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'to}^{R,DTRU} \quad (32a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRU} \geq -p_l^{\max} \cdot x_{ltb} + p_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{ldto}^{D,DTRU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRU} \geq -\Delta p_{dltto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (32b)$$

$$\lambda_{lwto}^{W,DTRU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{wto}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRU} \geq -\Delta p_{w'lto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{wto}^- \geq 0 \quad (32c)$$

$$\lambda_{ll'to}^{R,DTRU} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRU} \geq -\Delta p_{l'lto}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{lto}^- \geq 0 \quad (32d)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRZL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,DTRZL} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'to}^{R,DTRZL} \quad (33a)$$

$$-Y_{to} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZL} \geq 0 \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRZL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZL} \geq -\Delta p_{dto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (33b)$$

$$\lambda_{w'to}^{W,DTRZL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZL} \geq -\Delta p_{w'to}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (33c)$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRZL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZL} \geq -\Delta p_{l'to}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (33d)$$

$$-\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRZU} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,DTRZU} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRZU} \quad (34a)$$

$$-\Upsilon_{lto} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZU} \geq -\Delta \bar{p}_{lto} \cdot z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRZU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZU} \geq \Delta p_{dto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (34b)$$

$$\lambda_{w'to}^{W,DTRZU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZU} \geq \Delta p_{w'to}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (34c)$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRZU} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZU} \geq \Delta p_{l'to}^a + z_{r|line(r)=l} \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L \mid l = l', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (34d)$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRZU} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRZU} \geq \Delta p_{l'to}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L \mid l \neq l', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (34d)$$

$$\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRXL} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{wto}^{W,DTRXL} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRXL} \quad (35a)$$

$$-\Upsilon_{lto} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXL} \geq 0 \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O$$

$$\lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRXL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXL} \geq -\Delta p_{dto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \quad (35b)$$

$$\lambda_{w'to}^{W,DTRXL} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXL} \geq -\Delta p_{w'to}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (35c)$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRXL} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXL} \geq -\Delta p_{l'to}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \quad (35d)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\Delta p_{lto}^n - \sum_{d \in \Omega^D} \hat{p}_{dto}^+ \cdot \lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRXU} - \sum_{w \in \Omega^W} \hat{p}_{wto}^- \cdot \lambda_{lwto}^{W,DTRXU} - \sum_{l' \in \Omega^L} \Delta \hat{p}_{lto}^- \cdot \lambda_{l'to}^{R,DTRXU} \\
& -\Upsilon_{to} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXU} \geq -\Delta \bar{p}_{lto} \cdot x_{lto} \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O
\end{aligned} \tag{36a}$$

$$\lambda_{dto}^{D,DTRXU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{dto}^+} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXU} \geq \Delta p_{dto}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, d \in \Omega^D, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{dto}^+ \geq 0 \tag{36b}$$

$$\lambda_{lw'to}^{W,DTRXU} + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_{w'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXU} \geq \Delta p_{w'to}^a \quad l \in \Omega^L, w' \in \Omega^W, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : p_{w'to}^- \geq 0 \tag{36c}$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRXU} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXU} \geq \Delta p_{l'l'to}^a + x_{lto} \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L \mid l = l', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \tag{36d}$$

$$\lambda_{l'l'to}^{R,DTRXU} + \frac{1}{\Delta \hat{p}_{l'to}^-} \cdot \lambda_{lto}^{Y,DTRXU} \geq \Delta p_{l'l'to}^a \quad l, l' \in \Omega^L \mid l \neq l', t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O : \Delta p_{l'to}^- \geq 0 \tag{36d}$$

Second-Stage Constraints on Dependent Variables:

$$0 \leq p_{bto} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \tag{37}$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \leq m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \tag{38}$$

$$\frac{p_{lto}}{y_l} - (\theta_{s(l)} - \theta_{r(l)}) \geq -m_l \cdot (1 - x_{lto}) \quad l \in \Omega^L, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \tag{39}$$

$$-\theta^{\max} \leq \theta_{bto} \leq \theta^{\max} \quad b \in \Omega^B, t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \tag{40}$$

$$\theta_{to}^{ref} = 0 \quad t \in \Omega^T, o \in \Omega^O \tag{41}$$